

City Marketing & Urban Branding: A New Way to Identify Egyptian Cities through Creating Positive Public Mental Image

Studying urban branding elements in the advertising Advertising Campaigns of Egyptian cities in the 21st century

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Abstract

Globalization contains new areas of research that still under development. Among these research is urban branding. It's an alternative for countries to promote and rebuild their image in order to attract business and tourism. The public mental image is the first engine to, attract develop and improve the place in consumer mind. It is a catalyst picture of urban design and manufacture of urban branding. The paper will study Advertising Campaigns on the Egyptian cities that carries distinctive mental image of its urban (physical, cultural, social, economic and urban elements) at the whole city. The city contains urban elements those elements are not individual, but related to each other creating the city limits physically and symbolically.

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Keywords

Urban Development; Mental Image; City Marketing; Nation Branding; Urban Branding & Marketing Campaign

1. Introduction

Cities, like dreams, are made of desires and fears, even if the thread of their discourse is secret, their rules are absurd, their perspectives deceitful, and everything conceals something else.

Italo Calvino, 1972

In today's globalized world, cities reflect our collective identity. Cities are the starting point for all human activities and therefore valuable networks that have created their own images and brands. The paper puts criticism of those urban elements on the basis of the modern urban planning theories and urban branding theories, then we describe the quantity and quality of those elements in Egyptian Advertising Campaigns with a preliminary study of some of the concepts of urban branding and their impact on the urban planning industry. After that the search will exposure to global examples in city marketing. Finally we can analyzing the performance of different actors on how countries promote its image abroad.

Generally, city marketing is strategy to provide cities with the brand identities, including positioning, brand personality, urban branding and nation branding. The function of city branding is a source of added symbolic. On the other hand, the traditional urban Planning aims to solving problems. The urban problem is an outdated concept nowadays people pursue higher quality of life. Urban branding and planning get closer in this era even they

supposes to be two separated disciplines. People buy a way of life through discussion and implication, there will be attempts to recap what it takes to urban branding, and further discuss if city should take the urban branding conceptual framework, and address how this approach would help Egyptian cities as a whole to brand its cities.

Research methodology

This paper utilizes a case study approach for urban branding topic. Through theoretical, analytical and practical view point. By making definition of city marketing, nation branding and urban branding. The theoretical part shown in two sections firstly, Simon Anholt nation brand hexagon six factors susceptible to affect a nation's image; people, culture and heritage, exports, government and investments and immigration. Secondly, studying urban branding strategies which support a credible identity through media, historical buildings, city form, signature architecture building. Taking into consideration that paper encompasses case study, of Egyptian marketing campaign "New Egypt, old friends".

1.1. Research Problem

There are deficiencies in the successful Urban Spaces representation in many Egyptian cities, which can be an effective tool in attracting tourists and investment, and on various aspects of disease from the track and forelock end to the distinctive signs to find out **several questions**

1. Does your image and branding reflect who you are and what do you now rather than what you have done in the past?
2. Is this campaign case reflect the six dimensions mentioned in the hexagon model and urban branding strategies?

1.2. Research Objectives

The objectives of research on the monitoring of urban elements help to create a positive mental image of the Egyptian cities of which the Egyptian authorities see elements of global and regional attraction to activate the economic situation

The purpose of the thesis is to analyze how these campaigns affect and promote the urban environment image of Egyptian cities in the world. Consequently, the aim of this paper is to analyze a specific case which could be worth for instance in order to gain global recognition.

1.3. Research hypothesis

When linking the results of the investigation to the concept of nation brand and urban branding through Athol's hexagon model and branding strategies show the aim of this paper is to analyze a specific case. The following hypothesis which links with one of the proposed questions will be tested:

When we promote to any city we need to use all of strategies and terms of marketing starting from city marketing then nation branding and urban branding to give the right image about place and city.

In particular, this paper could be taken as a practical case of urban branding between developed countries which can show interesting differences with the promotion conducted towards developing countries. Besides, the application of the Athol's model to a practical case of promotion campaign could give way to new questions or approaches.

1.4. Literature Review:

This paper is studying cities marketing and the modern urban environment theories .in this part some definition that supported the investigation of the paper will be shown.

2. City marketing, Nation branding & place branding

2.1. City marketing

Means designing a place to satisfy the needs of its target markets. It succeeds when citizens and businesses are pleased with their communities, and the expectations of visitors and investors are met. (Kotler et al. 1999,) city marketing includes several different trends and forms of branding: nation branding, place of origin branding, destination branding and city branding. Place and city uses branding as an approach to integrate, guide and focus place management. (Warnaby 2009)

It is a challenge to tell people that logos and slogans are not the brand, but that they can be a tool to communicate the brand at the end of a long process.

Zenker, Sebastian 2017

Marketers can draw tools to implement an effective image of a place: slogans, positions, themes and visual symbols (logos) or events and deeds. A city brand can be based on various attributes. Usually people think about cities in terms of qualities or some kind of story. Like “Paris is romance, Milan is style, New York is energy, Washington is power, Tokyo is modernity, Barcelona is culture, Rio is fun. These are the brands of cities, and they are inextricably tied to the histories and destinies of all these places.”(Anholt 2007).

Figure 1. Brand Dimension

It can be possible to link between city marketing ,urban branding & nation branding together to have our country campaigns vision .three trends focus on improving city image to communicate with their target audience .every trend has its strategies and tools .branding is one of marketing process which means that city marketing include nation branding and urban branding . City branding has to take under consideration the historical and cultural background, the social and the economic development, the landscape and the natural surroundings, the infrastructures and the architectural statements of the city and their possible interaction and combination to actually create a place with an enhanced monetary value (Zhang, 2009).

Figure 2. Relation between City Marketing and Branding Types

2.1.1. Urban Branding

the unique, multi-dimensional blend of elements that provide the city with culturally grounded differentiation and relevance for all of its target audiences

Dinnie 2008

The objectives of branding a city are attracting inward investment and tourists secondly, to reinforce local identity and identification of the citizens with their city thus, it can be argued that the ultimate goal of city branding is to foster the economic development of the city and to improve the wellbeing of its residents (Prilenska 2012).

In order to achieve this purpose, two main strategies can be developed; the creative or experience city strategy. These strategies seek to improve the image and reputation of the city in an attempt to foster inward development and improve the quality of life of its residents and, although both pursue the same goal, the implementation of each is relatively different.

- The creative city strategy breaks old prejudices and towards a city by showing its most innovative, alternative and high-tech side, making it more attractive for skillful individuals, For this to occur, the city must have the technology, tolerance and talent also called The Three T's of the creative class (Henze 2014). In addition to The Three T's, such a city should have qualitative and affordable housing, public services, short travel times among other cities, lifestyle and cultural opportunities and, lastly, quality of city spaces such as green and public areas.
- The experience city strategy is usually developed by those cities which, due to their size, location or history do not have potential for developing creative cities (Prilenska 2012). Place bound experiences include events, activities such as shopping, sports and artistic activities, services such as theme restaurants, wellness centers, art galleries and theatres and, lastly, different places which act as a host for diverse activities such as recreational parks, museums, sights...

2.1.2. Nation Branding

The nation's image becomes the reputation of the country.

(wee, f.woo, 2009)

A city's image reflects how people experience it and what the city is known for. An image highlights disparity and individuality. (Virtanen, 1998) .city's image is the sum of beliefs, ideas and impressions that people have of that place. Different people can hold quite different images of the same place. (Kotler etl, 1999) Image's mission is to individualize a city, separate it from other cities and give it its own identity.

Brand Identity There is a gap between the nation's identity and the nation's image. The brand identity is projected while the country's image is perceived. Brand identity indicates what a brand stands for: its history, purpose, principles and ambitions. There are no two brands alike with same core values, roots and visual identity. (Van Gelder 2003,)

Figure 3promotional Mix However, Brand image may turn out to be something entirely different as the planned identity, because image is subject to perception. The brand identity can be confusing or something entirely different than planned. This is called "the perception gap". Perception gap must be avoided by ensuring that the target audience sees and relates to the brand identity and acknowledges what is offered. (Temporal 2002).

3. Advertising Campaigns

Advertising campaigns is one of Promotions strategy of marketing mix .it delivers the brand image To create brand awareness and attract new customers .businesses have many choices of how and where to promote or advertise their products. Advertising Campaigns are the application of clear and consistent brand messaging using different promotional methods .The campaigns are designed to present the magnetism, strengths and competitive advantages of selected countries to an elite global audience.

Figure 3. Promotional Mix

3.1. Advertising Campaigns Critic Criteria

To critic Advertising Campaigns we need a strategic criterion based on specific elements to get the overall concept. Those used elements based on tow branding strategies (urban branding strategies & nation branding strategies) Firstly urban branding elements which contain the urban physical elements, secondly nation branding elements.

3.1.1. Urban Branding Elements

The process of developing often takes 10 to 20 years (Moilanen & Seppo, 2009). Most of the literature on urban branding and nation branding focuses on the means of building a brand. Robin D. Rusch, (2003) suggests that branding a city is not just coming up with a 'snappy logo'. There's a lot of strategic research and planning like

1. What sort of business or visitor are to be targeted?
2. What areas or features will in turn be attractive to these groups?
3. How the city life is looks like?
4. How city form reach target audience?
5. Which urban elements create the best mental image?
6. The existing perceptions either need to be enhanced to launch a credible identity.

The image that one has about another country shows how one sees that country; image and progress go hand in hand as a place to invest or as a source of goods. Therefore, country promotes its brands, those brands will promote the country, but what about urban elements which describe the physical features that define the character or image of the City as a whole (street, neighborhood, community). Urban design is the visual and sensory relationship between people and the built and natural environment. All of these questions it can be answered by here under elements of urban branding (shape 2).

The branding of urban elements has benefited from branding of the city, the city should benefit from the magnificent network of open spaces, waterfronts, and boulevards that is already in place, and the principal idea is to change the traditional face of city, to meet the rapid development of the city.

Figure 4. Urban Branding Elements

Through, branding of **city life** as a tool rendering the urban image new and active, (rehan, 2014) city life shows The City very attractive place in which to hold events and celebrations. Then prompt city as a cultural place which has **historical building** like mosques, opera house ,castles and new places .When city could attract international architects who design **landmarks** buildings that role is branding a city as a new icon it called “Signature Architecture Icons”. The urban image is featured in **media** (advertising campaigns, T.V, movies city publication, social media) using logos and slogans to extract characteristics and reach a goal. One of the main attraction branding elements is **city form** which includes public spaces.

Figure 5. Examples for Cities logos and slogans

3.1.2. Nation Branding Elements

In 2005, Anholt Gfk puts list started with 35 countries about nation branding, but nowadays the study rose to 50 nation. The in study measures the power and quality of each country’s brand image by combining the six channels represented in the hexagon model (Anholt Gfk-America, 2010). The study also allows to measuring the rating of one country towards another. Therefore we choose it to have accurate information about developing branding plans more focused.

The list of Anholt is based on the political and economic importance of the nations in global geopolitics and the flow owes, listed by six region North America, Western Europe, Central/Eastern Europe, Asia-Pacific, Latin America, and Middle East/Africa. Based on Anholt’s competitive identity, there are six pathways: tourism, export, governs, investment, culture, and people.

Figure 6. Anholt GFK six Path ways Chart

Table 1. Anholt GFK six Path ways

EXPORT	Determines the public’s image of products from each country and the extent to which consumer proactively seek or avoid products from each country of origin.
GOVERNS	Measures public opinion regarding the level of national government competency and fairness and describes individuals’ beliefs about each country’s government, as well as its perceived commitment to global issues such as democracy, justice, poverty and the environment.
INVESTMENT	Determines the power to attract people to live, work or study in each country and reveals how people perceive a country’s economic and social situation.
CULTURAL	Reveals global perceptions of each nation’s heritage and appreciation for its contemporary culture, including film, music, art, sport and literature.
PEOPLE	Measures the population’s reputation for competence, education, openness and friendliness and other qualities, as well as perceived levels of potential hostility and discrimination.
TOURISM	Captures the level of interest in visiting a country and the draw of natural and man-made tourist attractions.

Which include Anholt competitive identity, six pathways any government had to invested time and money to nurture all of these sectors: export, governs, investment, cultural, people, tourism. Although Enhancing the beauty and livability of the city by protecting its historic design legacy, reinforcing the identity of its neighborhoods, harmoniously integrating new construction with existing buildings and the natural environment, and improving the vitality, appearance, and security of streets and public spaces.

Figure 7. Nation Branding Elements

4. Case Study (NEW EGYPT, OLD FRIENDS) 2016 Campaign

Egypt Well Known As

If we look at the branded image of Egypt outside of Egypt, there are primarily things that come to people’s minds. Egypt’s identity is defined by a particular set of physical features, including Nile River, the topographic Sahara that surrounds it. One of dominant symbols in the formal and semi formal sphere derives mainly from aspects of Egypt’s history, especially the Pharaonic and Islamic periods. The three Giza pyramids with the Great Sphinx represents the most important and obvious visual symbol of the Egyptian nation.

2008-2014 Score Change by Panel Countries

	Total	Argentina	Australia	Brazil	Canada	China	Egypt	France	Germany	India	Italy	Japan	Mexico	Poland	Russia	South Africa	South Korea	Sweden	Turkey	United Kingdom	United States
Nation Brands	2.0	-0.5	3.2	3.6	4.2	6.0	4.5	-1.1	4.2	1.0	1.5	0.8	0.8	1.1	3.4	0.1	2.3	1.3	2.7	2.1	0.4
Exports	1.7	-0.5	3.7	2.7	3.5	7.5	4.1	-3.7	3.2	2.4	2.0	-0.1	-2.2	1.7	4.0	-1.0	-3.7	4.1	3.2	1.8	-0.4
Governance	0.8	-0.4	3.6	4.6	5.4	6.6	5.1	-1.1	3.9	-0.8	-1.4	1.2	-1.4	-2.8	-1.5	-2.1	0.7	0.3	1.7	1.8	0.2
Culture	1.1	-0.9	2.1	0.0	2.2	4.9	-1.7	1.1	3.3	1.3	0.1	-0.2	-0.7	2.0	5.5	0.3	0.9	-0.2	3.7	0.8	-0.4
People	0.3	-1.1	2.7	3.6	2.4	3.1	6.6	-2.6	2.2	-0.4	-1.7	-0.3	2.4	-2.7	2.5	-1.5	0.0	-1.8	-0.5	1.0	1.4
Tourism	0.3	-0.7	0.2	3.4	1.7	2.8	3.8	-1.1	2.8	0.0	1.8	-1.1	-0.9	0.3	2.3	-0.8	0.0	-2.2	0.2	-0.1	-2.9
Immigration-Investment	7.5	5.5	6.9	7.9	9.3	11.1	9.3	2.7	9.5	9.3	7.9	5.5	7.6	9.1	7.1	5.3	8.2	8.1	8.4	7.4	4.5
Ex-Science&Technology	0.1	-0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.1	-0.3	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.4	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.1	-0.1
Ex-Buy products	0.1	-0.2	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.8	0.4	0.0	0.3	0.2	0.2	-0.1	-0.3	0.1	0.0	-0.2	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0
Ex-Creative Place	0.2	-0.2	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.2	-0.2	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.4	-0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.0
Gov-Competent&Honest	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.2	-0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1
Gov-Flights&Fairness	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.3	-0.3	0.2	-0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.3	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	-0.1
Gov-Peace&Security	0.0	-0.1	0.3	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.2	-0.2	0.3	-0.2	0.0	0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.0
Gov-Environment	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.2	-0.4	0.4	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0
Gov-Poverty	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.5	-0.1	0.3	0.0	-0.3	0.1	-0.2	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.1	0.1
Cul-Sports	0.1	-0.1	0.2	-0.1	0.3	0.3	-0.3	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.3	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.0
Cul-Cultural Heritage	0.1	-0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	-0.2	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.4	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	-0.1
Cul-Contemporary Culture	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.3	0.2	0.0
Peo-Welcoming	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.4	-0.1	0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.2	0.2	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	0.3	0.1	0.1
Peo-Close Friend	0.1	-0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.4	-0.1	0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.4	-0.1	0.1	-0.2	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.1
Peo-Employability	0.0	-0.3	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.4	-0.3	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	-0.3	0.1	0.2
Tou-Visit if Money No Obiect	0.0	-0.3	-0.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.5	-0.1	0.3	-0.2	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	-0.3
Tou-Natural Beauty	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.2	0.4	-0.3	0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	0.0	0.0	-0.1
Tou-Historic Buildings	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.3	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.1	-0.2
Tou-Vibrant City	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.2
Wl-Work&Live	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.5	-0.4	0.1	-0.1	0.3	0.0	0.4	0.2	-0.2	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.4	0.0	0.1
Wl-Quality of Life	0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.1	-0.2	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	-0.2	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.2	-0.2
Wl-Educational Qualifications	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.4	0.1	-0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.2	0.4	-0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Wl-Invest in Business	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	-0.3	0.1	0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.2
Wl-Equality in Society	0.1	0.4	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.1	0.4	0.3	0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.4	0.1

Note: The cells are colored using Excel conditional formatting. Green show positive changes and red negative changes. Changes reflect the raw, and not indexed, score change.

Figure 8. Egypt degrees around 50 country in 2008, 2014 GFK panel & NBIst

“In 2008 culture index of GFK & NBISM” Egypt ranked as 4th place in 50 country, which widely known for their cultural and ancient civilizations, get their best scores in this dimension, lifted primarily by the “rich cultural heritage”.

“New Egypt, Old Friend” campaign created by QCP TV Company, an award-winning International production company and the exclusive TV producer for some of the world’s leading countries and News Channels throughout Europe, Africa, Middle East and Latin America, ..etc, created the campaign “New Egypt, Old Friends”, which gives the campaign a professional character.

The campaign focuses on Egypt as country at all. It showed a lot of Egyptian cities (Luxor, red sea region, Suez) but the most one has appeared the capital Cairo.

Cities in Campaign

Cairo: The architecture and layout of the city reflect the various epochs of its history. Very roughly, old Cairo is the medieval part, the heart of popular Cairo, and also where the Islamic and Coptic monuments are. The modern city center was built in the nineteenth century and was model dafter Paris. New Cairo include open spaces and parks and modern compounds, and the wide diagonal boulevards and rectangular street grid. The city is further defined by its horizontal skyline in Nile valley contain the region’s tallest buildings while the central city is characterized by lower buildings of relatively uniform mass and height. **Luxor** it is one of the oldest cities in the world, but the campaign doesn’t use it. The Carnac temple appeared in one scene **Red sea region & Suez.**

Figure 9. Egypt Map Shows Important Cities

4.1. Urban Branding Elements through Egyptian Campaign

Media- generated image

Logo & Slogan: the combination between slogan and logo considered an essential starting point for any urban branding campaign. It is also a difficult tool to use: a poorly chosen slogan or logo can haunt a city for many years. Here they use a complicated logo (figure 10) contain lots of architecture elements (Alex library, three pyramids and sphinx, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Neil Towers, Bridge peace commentator, Cairo Tower, the new Egyptian museum).

Figure 10. complicated logo used in the campaign (New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

They didn't follow New York In 1977, when they decided to combat increasingly negative images by using new logo "I Love NY" its short and to the point.

The message from such example is developing a coherent and convincing 'story'. For both large and small cities finding a story or even a set of stories .for Slogan, they use the same name of the campaign to be the slogan. In 2004, Singapore launching "uniquely Singapore" campaign, which had the same slogan name.

"New Egypt Old Friends"

Website: it doesn't show any connection channels website or different types of social media, just logos of companies that appeared in the campaign.

Signature Architecture

It is an approach to marketing and advertising places. Buildings have a power and tangible symbolic value. These building have different functions, such buildings become icons but also act as magnets for investments, tourists and labor, like the Great Pyramids is an inherent part of how we understand and think of our home (countries/cities). Some buildings, like the Twin Towers, retain their symbolic meaning even after their distortion. The grand Egyptian museum (largest archeological museum) took a big part of campaign because it's fit with concept of new Egypt. The Museum hopefully will generate a huge success in changing the image of the urban fabric around it especially when linking it with the great pyramids and attracted national and international media coverage during planning and construction.

Figure 11. Shows the iconic grand Egyptian museum(New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

Figure 12. Shows the iconic great pyramids in Giza(New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

Branding Urban Projects/ Flag Ship Projects

New large-scale projects, culture project and new internationally recognized buildings like Moutain view (Cairo, North coast, sokhna), dream land & smart village, those compounds developers can make up a vital part of an urban branding strategy. It also assumes the guise of energetic redevelopment programs for the place. The goal is to use culture as a flag that attracts new residents or whether there is a concerted attempt to create cultural industries clusters.

Figure 13. Shows flag ships projectssmart village , mountain view (New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

City form

It's one of important branding elements strategy Public spaces around Nile valley, its main attraction point of Egypt as an environmental public space and international hotels. Parks privet compound parks had been shown, Landmarks to develop a memorial statue like t.v. building maspero tower and Cairo tower .there is no memorial statue .Libraries despite Egypt have one of the most important libraries in the world .the campaign doesn't benefit from it .Museums the grand Egyptian museum used as an iconic building, and no one also showed to make an unique image for Egypt. Modern streets Moaaz Street used as modern and developed street.

Figure 14. shows public spaces, (Nile valley – Alazhar park) (New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

Historical places

It's one of the striking visitor's sights and the campaign showed very little historical places like (Hatshepsut temple, Giza pyramids, Mohamed Ali mosque, Moaaz Street).

Figure 15. Historical places (hatshepsut temple – Muhammad Ali mosque) , (New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

Brand city life

Various events and cultural activities seem to be always new and rich characterized country. Events had been shown Egypt economic development conference /financial services events, and Cultural activities dancing party nights.

4.2. Nation branding Elements through Egyptian Campaign

Tourism

Vibrant city Cairo appeared as the only vibrant city, despite there was another rich cities with Historical buildings like Karnack temple in Luxor, Giza and great pyramids, and throw Natural beauty of urban environmental spaces like desert and under the sea life these all with Visit if money no object.

Figure 16. Events with different purposes used in Egypt (New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

People

The campaign used different celebrities in defiant fields ministers, the president, singers, stylist, investor, but it couldn't connect all those people together like the my Houston campaign (2013) when all celebrities use the same slogan at the end of their word about the city "these is my Houston". Employability it showed biomedical, engineering and construction facilities to tell the world how to invest in our country. Close friend it showed the Egyptian people Welcoming and happy.

Figure 17. Some public figures in Egypt (New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

Culture

The campaign focuses on Contemporary culture more than cultural heritage and Sports like (golf, diving, parachute para-sailing) just two seconds of the campaign.

Figure 18. Used sports in the campaign (New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

Governance

The campaign doesn't mention Poverty, Environment, Peace & security, Rights & fairness, Competent & honest of these section, because it wasn't the target of the campaign.

Exports

It focused on Creative place like Suez channel expansion project it is a logistics hub which will improve the place around it and guide to logistic city. Buy products it used the Egyptian stock exchange/ central bank of Egypt to give the image of new improved economy. Here is one of Science & technology filed pharmaceutical industry and Archaeology science had been shown.

Figure 19. improving exports road through Suez canal Expansion (New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

Immigration

Quality in society it didn't mention, Invest in business construction field, pharmaceutical industry is the most investment used there and trading with other countries throw new expansion of Suez channel. Educational they didn't mention any type of it.

Figure 20. Some logistic projects (New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

Quality of life shows the luxury life, and they didn't mention those people residents or visitors. **Work & live** it showed throw employee in several pioneering developments and banks.

Figure 21. The quality in sosaiety life , work & live (New Egypt Old Friends, 2016)

5. Summary

The campaign covered different types of urban branding strategies and nation branding but without mention names. It connected architectural elements with logo but also there was no slogan to link all parts of the campaign to make one identity. It focused on new construction project to show how many operations on Egypt, there for it neglected the historical part an important landmarks, event, activities.

6. Conclusion

City branding theory is still in an emergent phase. Egypt should embark on nation, urban branding because it has many elements somewhat in place. Egypt tries to stay current and relevant; and it evolves with the present global environment. Egypt is competing for affluent residents (investment) and tourists. Egypt should take on nation, urban branding to position itself to compete in the global market.

It needs to define its own brand identity. From that identity, have all the stakeholders work towards a cohesive

brand. There should also be a flow of communications to share a common goal. Transparency is essential in this communication process to keep things on track.

- Egypt needs to identify and recognized its own identity.
- Egypt should first research, and find out what is the public’s view on Egypt’s identity.
- To successfully nation brand, Egypt will require more foundation data.
- The campaign doesn’t mention any city name or nick name ,so if you want to visit cities and related urban element you wouldn’t have information to do .

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